

Kinetics and mechanism of electron-transfer reactions : Light induced bleaching of methyl orange by peroxodisulphate in the presence of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_3^{2+}]$ photocatalyst in aqueous solution

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Abstract : The kinetics of oxidative bleaching of methyl orange induced by irradiation with visible light in the presence of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_3^{2+}]$ as a photocatalyst has been studied. It is the azo group of the dye that undergoes oxidation by the sulphate free radical, the latter is generated in quenching of the excited state of the catalyst by peroxodisulphate. A plausible reaction mechanism has been suggested. The quenching rate constant has been calculated by employing life time of the excited state. These results have also been compared with the results obtained in the dye-persulphate reaction in the presence of silver(I) as catalyst. $[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_3^{2+}]$ has been found to be a better photocatalyst than silver(I).

Keywords : Kinetics, bleaching, methyl orange, persulphate, $\text{Ru}^{II}(\text{bipy})_3$.

Such methods which are related to chemical oxidation in solution are usually considered to be important more particularly for the treatment of industrial waste-water or polluted water which are known to contain non-biodegradable materials. The substrates which are available for studies of chemical oxidation but not suitable for conventional treatment of activated sludge of which large quantities are available in textile effluents¹.

The triaryl methane dyes are known to enter aquatic environment and are reportedly² studied in detail. Rate and equilibrium constants for poly aryl methane dyes and a wide range of nucleophiles are well co-related. Peroxodisulphate is, however, the cleanest oxidant of choice from the viewpoint of environment.

The possible source of organic pollution is the waste arising from industrial processes which utilize dyes to colour paper, plastics, natural and artificial fibres. It is surprising that despite the intense research activity in the field of semiconductor photo catalysts for purification of water, a little work has been directed at the level of its applications to the photomineralization of photostable dyes³⁻⁶.

Recently two research papers on copper(II) and manganese(II) catalyzed oxidation of calmagite dye by peroxosulphate in alkaline media have been reported^{7,8}. Calmagite is a dye containing *o,o'*-dihydroxy azo structure. Similar is rhodamine G, an azo dye with a change in structure from the methyl orange. Thus, if the reaction events of bleaching of methyl orange dye are revealed as has been

revealed in laser photochemistry, better reaction model for oxidative bleaching of the dye can be exploited for reasonable understanding and suitable applications in the treatment of sludge.

These were certain observations of the bleaching that prompted us to undertake the kinetic study of the title reaction with the main objectives as follows :

First azo dyes such as calmagite or rhodamine G are known to form strong complexes with metal ions in aqueous acid medium. However, no such metal-complexation is reported^{7,8} in case of methyl orange; Does azo group present in the compound not participate in metal complexation!

Secondly *cis-trans* thermal tautomerization is a well known⁹ chemical phenomenon in methyl orange mechanism. How is this tautomerization significant so far the chemical events are concerned; Does the mechanism in the presence of photocatalysts invoke such an idea of tautomerization! or a different mechanism is found for such a bleaching process.

Thirdly does mineralization of the dye in the presence of photocatalyst take place! or it simply goes to the stage of oxidative bleaching.

Experimental

Materials : Methyl orange dye (E. Merck) a sodium salt was employed as a fresh sample without any further treatment and the solution was kept in a glass bottle painted black from the outside at ambient temperature. The solution was standardized spectrally. The details regarding preparation and

standardization of other reagents employed in this study are already mentioned elsewhere¹⁰. All solutions were prepared in doubly distilled water.

Table 1. Initial rates, pseudo-first order and second order rate constants in silver(i) catalyzed oxidative bleaching of methyl orange by peroxodisulphate

Temp. 30 °C, $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 500 \text{ nm}$

$10^3 [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	10^5 [Methyl orange] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^3 [\text{Ag}^+]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^7 (k_i)$ (mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹)	k (mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹)
1.0	5.0	1.0	0.21	2.1
2.0	5.0	1.0	0.45	2.3
3.0	5.0	1.0	0.58	1.9
4.0	5.0	1.0	0.90	2.3
5.0	5.0	1.0	1.1	2.2
7.0	5.0	1.0	1.54	2.2
8.0	5.0	1.0	1.72	2.2
10.0	5.0	1.0	2.18	2.2
1.0	10.0	1.0	0.19	1.9
2.0	10.0	1.0	0.42	2.1
3.0	10.0	1.0	0.60	2.0
4.0	10.0	1.0	0.90	2.3
5.0	10.0	1.0	1.15	2.3
7.0	10.0	1.0	1.54	2.2
8.0	10.0	1.0	1.79	2.2
10.0	10.0	1.0	2.18	2.2
2.0	1.0	1.0	0.40	2.0
2.0	2.0	1.0	0.42	2.1
2.0	3.0	1.0	0.42	2.1
2.0	4.0	1.0	0.42	2.1
2.0	5.0	1.0	0.42	2.1
2.0	7.0	1.0	0.44	2.2
2.0	8.0	1.0	0.44	2.2
2.0	10.0	1.0	0.42	2.1
4.0	2.0	1.0	0.90	2.3
4.0	3.0	1.0	0.90	2.3
4.0	4.0	1.0	0.90	2.3
4.0	5.0	1.0	0.90	2.3
4.0	7.0	1.0	0.90	2.3
4.0	8.0	1.0	0.90	2.3
4.0	10.0	1.0	0.90	2.3
4.0	10.0	2.0	1.54	1.9
4.0	10.0	3.0	2.44	2.0
4.0	10.0	4.0	3.33	2.1
4.0	10.0	5.0	4.10	2.1
Average			=	2.2

Doubly distilled water was employed, the second distillation being from alkaline potassium permanganate solution in an all glass still.

Initial rates were computed employing plane mirror

method¹⁰. Pseudo-first order plots were also made wherever reaction conditions permitted. Rates in triplicate were reproducible to within $\pm 5\%$.

Kinetic procedure :

The details regarding the vessels employed for reaction mixtures have already been mentioned¹⁰. These reaction mixtures were, however, purged by passing N₂ gas for at least 15 min prior to initiating the reaction and was also not interrupted even during the reaction. Aliquots (5 cm³) of the reaction mixture were withdrawn periodically employing hypodermic syringes through the side arm of the vessel sealed with a rubber septum. The presence of oxygen in the reaction mixture was qualitatively tested time and again and the test was found negative confirming the fact that oxygen was never in contact with the reaction mixture. The kinetics were monitored periodically at 500 nm employing 'Bausch and Lomb Spectronic 21' in a cell of one cm path length. It has also been reported that photo bleaching of methyl orange dye appears at $< 516 \text{ nm}$. This shows that an appropriate wave length at which photo bleaching must occur should always be $< 516 \text{ nm}$ although the spectrum of methyl orange extends upto *ca.* 580 nm. The temperature of the reaction mixture was kept constant by circulating water at the controlled bath temperature of the thermostat ($\pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$). Nevertheless, temperature variation in the range (25–40 °C) does not indicate any impact on such a photochemical reaction as has also been confirmed in earlier reactions.

Results

The concentration of peroxodisulphate was varied in the range $(1.0\text{--}5.0) \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at two different but fixed concentrations of the methyl orange viz. 1×10^{-4} and 8.0×10^{-4}

Fig. 1. Variation of peroxodisulphate : $[\text{Ru}^{\text{II}}] = 1.0 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; light = 100 W; $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 500 \text{ nm}$; [methyl orange] = 8.0×10^{-5} (O) and 1.0×10^{-4} (●) mol dm⁻³.

10^{-5} mol dm $^{-3}$ respectively at constant concentration of [Ru^{II}] = 1.0×10^{-7} mol dm $^{-3}$ ([Ru(bipy) $_3^{2+}$] henceforth is written as Ru^{II} for simplicity). Initial rates were calculated and a plot of initial rate (k_i) against the concentration of the oxidant yielded initially a straight line and then on increasing persulphate concentration further, the rate tended towards a limiting value (Fig. 1).

The concentration of methyl orange was varied in the range 1.0×10^{-5} to 1.0×10^{-4} mol dm $^{-3}$ keeping fixed concentrations of the oxidant viz. 1×10^{-3} and 2.0×10^{-3} mol dm $^{-3}$ respectively at [Ru^{II}] = 1×10^{-7} mol dm $^{-3}$. The rates being independent of the initial concentrations of methyl orange indicate zero order with respect to the dye.

The pH of the reaction mixture was varied from 3.5 to 11.7 keeping constant concentrations of other reaction ingredients viz. [S $_2$ O $_8^{2-}$] = 2.0×10^{-3} mol dm $^{-3}$, [dye] = 1.0×10^{-4} mol dm $^{-3}$ and [Ru^{II}] = 1.0×10^{-7} mol dm $^{-3}$. Initial rates were found to be independent of the pH.

The effect of ionic strength was studied by employing NaCl and KCl (0.1–0.5) mol dm $^{-3}$, KNO $_3$ and NaNO $_3$ in the range (0.1–0.5) mol dm $^{-3}$ and similarly NaClO $_4$ and LiClO $_4$ in the range (0.1–0.5) mol dm $^{-3}$ at fixed concentrations of other reaction ingredients viz. [S $_2$ O $_8^{2-}$] = 2.0×10^{-3} mol dm $^{-3}$, [dye] = 1.0×10^{-4} mol dm $^{-3}$ and [Ru^{II}] = 1.0×10^{-7} mol dm $^{-3}$ at constant temperature and pH. The rate, however, remains unchanged on changing the concentrations of these electrolytes.

The effect of light intensity was studied by increasing the number of bulbs without disturbing the distance between reaction vessel and light source. Initial rates (k_i) in such an arrangement of irradiation of the reaction mixture is directly proportional to the light intensity (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Variation of light : [S $_2$ O $_8^{2-}$] = 2.0×10^{-3} mol dm $^{-3}$; [methyl orange] = 1.0×10^{-4} mol dm $^{-3}$; [Ru^{II}] = 1.0×10^{-7} mol dm $^{-3}$; λ_{\max} = 500 nm.

Fig. 3. A plot of $(k_i)^{-1}$ versus [S $_2$ O $_8^{2-}$] : [Ru^{II}] = 1.0×10^{-7} mol dm $^{-3}$; light = 100 W; λ_{\max} = 500 nm; [methyl orange] = 8.0×10^{-5} (○) and 1.0×10^{-4} (●) mol dm $^{-3}$.

The stoichiometry of the reaction is based on the identification of the azoxy compound – the oxidation product of methyl orange. The spectral characteristics of this product match very closely to that of the product obtained after oxidation of methyl orange by hydrogen peroxide¹¹. Moreover, these products show similar IR characteristics confirming that -N(CH $_3$) $_2$ group is not affected at all and the attacking site is azo group (-N=N-).

Discussion

Various aspects of photoinduced and thermally induced *cis-trans* isomerization and its mechanism have been a subject matter of studies over the past many years^{12–19}. The reversible isomerization of azobenzenes is a subject matter of current interest as azobenzenes known to be potential candidates in photoactive compounds for molecular devices, photochemical switching systems and the systems for information storage.

Methyl orange is a dye which exists exclusively in the azo form and contains no *ortho* substituents. Since it acts as a monodentate ligand, the dye has very low affinity for binding by metals. Monohydroxy azo-dyes or non-*ortho* substituted azo-dyes, methyl orange did not produce any evidence of metal binding. Infact, incorporation of *ortho* substituents like *o'*-carboxy, *o'*-sulphato into monohydroxy unit are reportedly failing in promoting significant evidence of metal binding. It is, therefore, clear that the role of catalyst is not through the binding of methyl orange. Kinetically we are also not finding such an evidence in the title reaction.

Laser excitation¹⁹ of solutions of methyl orange ($7 > \text{pH} > 5.0$) results in photo chemically induced *trans-cis* isomerization. Although the thermal *cis-trans* isomerization of azobenzenes is known^{20,21} to be catalyzed by Bronsted and Lewis acids.

The photoinduced chemistry occurs from the lowest excited state which is triplet and involves a MLCT transition. Electron transfer reactions of this species may involve either the oxidation or reduction of the excited state of [$^{\circ}\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_3^{2+}$] with the dominant process depending upon thermodynamic parameters such as the oxidation potentials of [$\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_3^{2+}$]/[$\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_3^{3+}$] or [$\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_3^{2+}$]/[$\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_3^+$] complex ion and on zero-zero-transition energy.

Peroxodisulphate ($\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$) is one of the most useful¹⁵ oxidative quenchers of the excited state [$^{\circ}\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_3^{2+}$] as it decomposes into two ions upon photo reduction minimizing back electron transfer reaction.

The sulphate radical ion is a potential oxidant and can oxidize ruthenium(II) complex ion to ruthenium(III) complex ion.

Such a situation holds good if (i) the electron transfer is the only mode of quenching mechanism of (^3CT) Ru^{II} by $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ and (ii) the electron transfer reaction is irreversible. Thus taking into account these facts and the experimental observations on bleaching of methyl orange by peroxodisulphate, the mechanism of light induced bleaching of methyl orange can be envisaged as follows :

Scheme 1

Such a mechanism leads to the rate law (7)

$$\frac{-d[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]}{dt} = \frac{k_q I_a \phi [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]}{k_o + k_q [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]} \quad (7)$$

where I_a is an intensity of absorbed light and ϕ is the efficiency of formation of excited species.

The reciprocal of the eq. (7) yields eq. (8).

$$(k_i)^{-1} = A + B[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]^{-1} \quad (8)$$

where A and B are empirical constants and do not depend upon pH of the reaction ($\text{pH} = 8.0$).

A plot of $(k_i)^{-1}$ versus $[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]^{-1}$ was made from the eq.(8) that yielded a straight line with non-zero intercept (Fig. 3). k_q was calculated from the ratio of A and B by employing the life time of the excited ruthenium complex. The value of k_q calculated to be $3.31 \times 10^8 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ is of the same order as was reported earlier.

Further an important conclusion is regarding the effect of temperature on the rate of the reaction. The rate is, however, found to be independent of temperature, k_o/k_q is independent of temperature within experimental uncertainty. This shows that the energy of activation for the quenching reaction is close to that of the non-radiative quenching of the photoexcited species. Since k_q was determined in close agreement with the value reported in measurements of quenching luminescence, this supports both the mechanism and the rate law as proposed earlier.

Thus in view of these experimental observations the reaction events in brief can be explained by the reaction Schemes 1 or 2 for oxidative bleaching of methyl orange in solution irradiated by visible light in the presence of ruthenium(II) complex ion.

The simple Schemes 1 or 2 highlighting details of the reaction events can be suggested as follows :

Silver(I) is considered to be well matured²³⁻²⁶ catalyst in its catalytic role in peroxodisulphate reactions. The initial steps usually assumed for such catalyzed oxidations are the one-electron redox processes.

The reactions (9) to (10) are analogous to the initial steps in the oxidation of organic compounds by Fenton's reagent²⁷ but differ in that

- (i) Fe³⁺ is capable to oxidize intermediate substrate radicals.
- (ii) Ag^{II} is stronger oxidant and is capable of oxidizing suitable substrates as well.

Consequently rapid reduction of Ag^{II} to Ag^I brings back Ag^I to catalyst redox cycle and thus accounts for the catalytic effect on the overall rate of the oxidation. Our primary interest in this reaction is simply to compare the catalytic potentiality of Ag^I to that of [Ru(bipy)₃²⁺].

The concentration of Ag^I was varied in the range (1.0–5.0) × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ at fixed concentrations of other reaction ingredients, a plot of rate versus [Ag^I] yields a straight line passing through the origin. Similarly, the concentration of peroxodisulphate was varied in the range (1.0–10.0) × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ keeping constant concentrations of other reaction ingredients viz. [methyl orange] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ and 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³ and [Ag^I] = 1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³. Initial rates were plotted against the concentrations of peroxodisulphate that yielded a straight line passing through the origin confirming first order with respect to the oxidant. Pseudo-first order plots for varying concentration of methyl orange were also made and these were found to be independent of the concentrations of the oxidant further confirming first order dependence with respect to peroxodisulphate. The concentration of methyl orange was varied in the range (1.0–10.0) × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³ at constant concentrations of other reaction ingredients, the rates were found to be independent of the concentration of methyl orange confirming zero order with respect to the dye.

Thus considering first order with respect to the catalyst and the oxidant each and zero order with respect to the dye, the mechanism for silver(I) catalyzed oxidative bleaching of methyl orange by peroxodisulphate can be envisaged as follows :

Such a mechanism leads to the rate law (16)

$$k_1 - k[Ag^I][S_2O_8^{2-}] \quad (16)$$

where k_1 and ' k ' are initial rate and observed composite second order rate constant respectively (Table 1), [Ag^I] and [S₂O₈²⁻] are gross analytical concentrations of silver(I) and peroxodisulphate respectively.

SO₄⁻ and Ag^{II} are the two intermediate species which are in competition for the initial attack on the substrate. Other intermediates such as hydroxyl radicals reported earlier to be formed in the oxidation of water by either Ag^{II},²⁸ or Ag^{III},²⁹ can attack the substrate. Different products are reportedly formed in Ag^I–S₂O₈²⁻ reaction with the substrate and that of OH radical with substrate. The possibility of the formation of Ag^{III} as an intermediate (eq. (17)) can be ruled out.

Such an equilibrium lies far to the left in acid medium and also Ag^{III} may be involved in the oxidation of water. The role of Ag^{III} has usually been invoked to account for the complex kinetics²⁶ of Ag^I–S₂O₈²⁻ oxidations and the involvement of Ag^{III} will not ascribe to a second order kinetics as is the case silver(II) to be an intermediate³⁰. Therefore, it is Ag^{II} and not Ag^{III} that is involved in the oxidative bleaching of methyl orange by peroxodisulphate. Thus the following reaction Scheme 3 accounts for the silver(I) catalyzed oxidation of the dye.

Scheme 3

So far the comparative pattern of kinetics of these reactions is concerned, following points are worth considering :

- (i) The rate in both of these catalyzed reactions does not depend upon the concentration of the dye. Thus, the dye is involved in a fast step of the reaction mechanism ascribing to an interaction with highly reactive intermediate species.

- (ii) In case of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_3^{2+}]$ catalyzed light induced bleaching of the dye, the order with respect to the oxidant is variable whereas it is first order in silver(I) catalyzed oxidative bleaching.
- (iii) Since light induced oxidation of methyl orange in the presence of $[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_3^{2+}]$ as a photocatalyst by peroxodisulphate is effective in an environment of nitrogen whereas silver(I) catalysis remains unchanged on changing reaction environment. It is simply due to the quenching potentiality of the oxygen that interferes in light induced reactions.
- (iv) There are reactions in which $[\text{Ru}(\text{bipy})_3^{2+}]$ degradation after a long time has been reported whereas no such chemical change is indicated in silver(I).
- (v) Light induced oxidative bleaching of the dye is not affected by the temperature upto $\sim 40^\circ\text{C}$ whereas the rate of silver(I) catalyzed reaction is significantly increased with the increasing of the temperature.

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